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Review Paper

Agricultural waste: Review of the evolution, approaches and perspectives on alternative uses

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ABSTRACT

This research provides an analysis of existing scientific production on agricultural waste from 1931 to 2018. The database was obtained from Scopus and includes a total of 3148 articles, which were analysed using the bibliometric method. This method focuses on the identification, evolution, approaches and trends referred to in the use and transformation of agricultural waste. The results of the analysis of the most specific variables, some of which are represented graphically through clusters in networking maps using VOSviewer software, establishes that agricultural waste has been studied worldwide for more than 60 years and that research on this issue has become more relevant from 1998. However, it has been in the last 13 years that more than 60% of the scientific production on this field of study has been generated. The United States, India and China are the countries with the greatest number of studies, whose central axis has been the use and exploitation of agricultural residues, derived from cereal crops, mainly wheat and corn, as they are the main producers of this type of crops. Many authors, mainly from government and academic institutions, have contributed considerably to this research topic. The evolution of their studies evidences a change in the original approach, due to the influence of the new global energy and environmental policies developed during the last decade. Undoubtedly, the international regulatory framework on sustainable development has been transforming the role of agriculture and especially the policies and strategies on the circular economy and bioeconomy. New and better techniques for the recovery of agricultural waste have been developed, based on industrial innovation and high technology, which has contributed to guaranteeing resource efficiency, sustainable production and consumption and the reduction of negative environmental impact.

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1. Introduction

During the Second World War (1939–1945), the need to improve production and distribution of food gained importance, in order to guarantee the adequate nutrition and health of people worldwide (FAO, 1948). After seven years of war, governments prioritized the restoration of the food system with the aim to solve hunger and malnutrition problems. In 1945, the

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Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) was created as a specialised body of the United Nations, which at that time was composed of 44 nations (FAO, 2015a). Since then, agriculture has become a major resource to reduce poverty and contribute to improving the standard of living of world's population, and the FAO has 149 members (FAO, 2017g).

The recovery of world agriculture after the war was gradual (FAO, 1947). The fluctuations in production in different regions during the early postwar years, was due to the negative impacts that were more serious than in the first world war (FAO, 1949). For 8000 years, cereals such as maize, wheat and rice have been the staple food supply for humans and animals worldwide (FAO, 2001a, 2015b). The major cereal producing countries are the United States, China, India, Brazil and the European Union (FAO, 1999, 2003). The Green Revolution has been one of the major contributions of the FAO to transform global agriculture (FAO, 2017a), the important increase of high yield cereal crop varieties (wheat and rice) in developing countries such as India and Mexico between 1960 and 1970 (Evenson and Gollin, 2003; Jhamtani, 2011), contributed to millions of people overcoming poverty (FAO, 2004).

Future projections predict higher growth in agricultural production, wherein end purposes are not only limited to food for the global population (FAO, 2017b), but also use as animal food and industrial needs. The rapid growth of bioenergy production from biofuel (Hazell and Pachauri, 2006) is an example of agricultural crop diversification in recent years, especially those crops with a high content of starch and cellulose. For example, the cereal starch, mainly derived from maize and wheat, is mostly used as raw material to produce ethanol (FAO, 2008a). Agricultural vegetal wastes, known as biomass, have an important potential to produce sustainable energy from renewable fuels (FAO and UNEP, 2010).

In 2006, bioenergy represented 10% of world energy (Hazell and Pachauri, 2006). Between 2000 and 2015, biofuel production significantly influenced increased crop demand (FAO and OECD, 2019a). In 2009, some experts recognised the close link between energy and agriculture and warned about a possible risk of food production for direct human consumption (FAO, 2009a). At that time, it was foreseen that the total demand for cereals would depend on the increase in biofuel demand and the expansion of technology designed to transform agricultural biomass into bioproduct (FAO, 2009b).

In 2018, cereal production increased compared with 2017, and Asia became the major producer (FAO, 2018). This increase in biofuel production was mainly due to some countries introducing compulsory regulation to mix this bioproduct with traditional fuel. The United States, Brazil, China and the European Union are among the major ethanol producers (FAO and OECD, 2017).

Agricultural production has increased more than three times over the last 50 years because of: the expansion of soils for agricultural use; the technological contribution of the green revolution which influenced productivity; and the accelerated growth of population (FAO, 2017c; FAO and OECD, 2019b). Agriculture produces an average of 23.7 million food tons per day worldwide (FAO, 2017c). This growth in worldwide production has created greater pressure on the environment, up to the point of causing negative impacts on soil, air and water resources (FAO, 2017d), with subsequent influences population health and the sustainability of ecosystems put at risk. Agriculture is responsible for 21% of greenhouse gases emissions. In recent years, this new situation has driven a model with more sustainable development, which implies important changes in the current agricultural production systems (FAO, 2016a).

For more than 30 years, the Report of the World Commission on Environment and Development has alerted us to the profound crisis of the environment due to accelerated population growth, which has increased the demand for natural resources, in order to improve economic development (UN, 1987; Vaz et al., 2017). At the same time, nations have been urged to articulate and coordinate political actions through a global program for change that would allow them to assume the responsibility of managing natural resources to ensure durable human progress (Ciegis et al., 2009; Halisçelik and Soytaş, 2019). From the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development (1992), the approach of a new model of sustainable development was consolidated, which implies the integration of economic, social and environmental factors to guarantee the welfare and improvement in the quality of life of the populations (UN, 2002, 2011).

These new evolutionary guidelines for governments have been oriented since then by global development objectives such as the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), defined in 2010, and the new Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development, approved in 2015, with 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and 169 targets that reflect the desire and compromise of world leaders to implement strategies and policies oriented towards the preservation of natural resources in order to guarantee environmental sustainability (UN, 2015a,b; FAO, 2017e). These new global goals pose the need for real structural reform in the world economy (Fukuda-Parr, 2016) to reduce the environmental degradation that threatens the future of humanity. Thus, according to the recent United Nations Sustainable Development Goals Report 2019 (UN, 2019a,b), the measures adopted until now have not been enough to make satisfactory progress in achieving these SDGs in the next 10 years. More ambitious and rapid measures are required from governments, focused on the efficient use of natural resources and the integration of sustainability criteria in all sectors of the economy, to ensure a real social and economic transformation (UN, 2018).

The priority of world leaders is not only to mitigate the impacts already caused, but also to respond to the need to produce more food and energy for a population that will exceed 10 billion people by 2050. All this must be achieved with less fossil fuel, lower emissions of polluting gases and zero solid waste (EC, 2018; UN, 2019a). This challenge has started to materialize through some regulatory and management instruments, such as the Europe 2020 Strategy of the European Union, issued in 2014 (EC, 2014, 2015), which aims to ensure smart, sustainable and inclusive growth for Europe. This general framework established the base line for the implementation of initiatives oriented towards sustainable production and consumption, among them, the strategy of Circular Economy and Bioeconomy (EC, 2015). The European Union adopted in 2012 their strategy of bioeconomy "innovating for sustainable growth" (updated in 2018) (European Commission, 2012a, 2012b, 2018a)

and in 2015, the Action Plan for the Circular Economy (EU, 2015). In this regard, the European Commission defines the bioeconomy as “the renewable segment of the circular economy” (EC, 2018b), and the German Bioeconomy Council (2015) stipulates that in the process of production and use of biological resources, innovation and research are key for the supply of products and services in all sectors in the context of a sustainable economy (Fund et al., 2018; Von Braun, 2018). Both perspectives are focused on economic aspects and on society’s transition to sustainability (EEA, 2018). More than 40 countries have developed and adopted national policies, policy instruments and strategies related to this new economic model in the last decade (EEA, 2017; Dietz et al., 2018; Molina-Moreno et al., 2017, 2016; Molina-Sánchez et al., 2018; Valenti et al., 2019), which is mainly based on an efficient resource management system in which the priority is to extend the useful life of materials and products and prevent their loss of value by incorporating their waste into production processes (Blomsma and Brennan, 2017; Molina-Moreno et al., 2017).

Ensuring resource efficiency is one of the main methods for mitigating climate change and achieving compliance with many of the SDGs (United Nations Economic and Social Council, 2017). This is why this model of circular economy plays a transcendental role by becoming the main alternative to traditional linear production practices (Núñez-Cacho et al., 2018), such as reuse, recycling, remanufacturing (Blomsma and Brennan, 2017; Górecki et al., 2019; Núñez-Cacho et al., 2018a), which contribute to the development of more sustainable production and consumption processes, ensuring the reduction of negative externalities (Górecki et al., 2019; Molina-Moreno et al., 2018). The circular economy and the bioeconomy contribute significantly to the achievement of four SDGs. Specifically, SDG 2: “Ending hunger, achieving food security and improving nutrition, and promoting sustainable agriculture”; SDG 11: “Making cities and human settlements inclusive, safe, resilient and sustainable”; SDG 12: “Ensuring sustainable consumption and production patterns”, the main purpose of which is “doing more and better with fewer resources” (UN, 2016) and SDG 13: “Taking urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts”.

Agriculture is one of the largest biological sectors with the highest biomass production (EC, 2015), which becomes an essential input for the bioeconomy, (Bracco et al., 2018; European Commission, 2012). This represents a great opportunity, not only because its use and exploitation favors the reduction of fossil fuel use and greenhouse gas emissions (McCormick and Kautto, 2013), but also because it contributes to the development of new green markets and jobs by promoting the conversion of vegetable waste into value-added products (by-products), such as food, feed, bioproducts and bioenergy (EC, 2017; EU, 2013; Scarlat et al., 2015; Mohanty et al., 2002). The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) has been reformed to prioritize and facilitate the adoption of the circular bioeconomy, providing support and incentives to farmers to optimize and make an efficient use of resources throughout the value chain, encouraging the valorization of biomass resources (EC, 2017a, 2019).

The evolution and current regulations of global policies and guidelines on the development of countries show increasing attention to global change, generated by a consumer society, which is responsible for the acceleration in the rate of extraction of natural resources and the generation of enormous amounts of waste, which, at the current rate of production and consumption, is estimated to double by 2050, amounting to 4 billion tons (UN, 2019; Zulkifli et al., 2019). Similarly, this new political framework reflects the urgency of facing climate change and sustainable development as major global and local challenges. Agriculture has become one of the largest and most important economic sectors for many countries and the largest generator of jobs worldwide (FAO, 2017f). This makes the transition to sustainable agriculture a priority, focusing on prevention of environmental impacts, through the adoption of innovative technological systems (Zulkifli et al., 2019).

This justifies the interest of this investigation, the main objective of which is to analyze the evolution of scientific production on waste and/or agricultural waste since the first publication contained in the database Scopus, dating from 1931 until 2018, to identify the relevance of this subject as a field of study and its correlation with political and/or global guidelines that have been issued in sustainability. Thus, the relevance of this theme is identified as a field of study along with its correlation with global policies and/or guidelines that have been developed in terms of sustainability. Therefore, two main research questions are posed: Have the techniques for the valuation of agricultural waste changed over the period analysed? Is there a relationship between agricultural waste research and the policies and/or guidelines issued under the sustainable development model? Is there any relationship between research on agricultural residues and policies and/or guidelines issued under the sustainable development model?

Among the variables evaluated in this bibliometric study, there are the main research approaches, the thematic areas to which the scientific articles belong, as well as authors, institutions and countries with the highest number of contributions to this field of science. The bibliometric method is considered an emerging research area, which is characterized by its quantitative approach, for the description and processing of academic papers (Kannan and Thanuskodi, 2019). This can be verified through the numerous publications that use this methodology from 1987 to 2019 (Bennell and Thorpe, 1987; Clarke et al., 2007; Fu, 2010; Abad-Segura et al., 2019; Aznar-Sánchez et al., 2018; Gómez-Ríos and Ramírez-Malule, 2019; Belmonte-Ureña et al., 2020).

The results of this study are a useful input to political leaders who are in the process of adjusting and articulate their programs and/or local development plans, with the ODS, especially those related to the circular bioeconomy. This work will also serve to identify the terminology related to agricultural biomass residues, the main techniques for the recovery of these wastes, as well as the relevance of this topic gained in recent years because it is an essential part of the new sustainable development model. These aspects are also relevant for farmers and other stakeholders in agricultural systems, as they are in the process of transitioning to this new economic model.

The identification of the principal authors, countries and institutions that have worked on this subject will help the actors involved in this field of study to recognize the references and/or potential allies, given their interest, extensive experience and

capacity investment in research, which could support processes and/or guide the decision-making or implementation processes. This aspect could be useful for the same researchers and public and private institutions who have contributed to scientific production to identify other partners with common objectives with whom they could create links to work in a coordinated manner and advance this important area that will continue to increase in importance.

2. Methodology

2.1. Method and bibliometric variables

The assessment of scientific literature concerning the field of study was carried out through a bibliometric analysis. Bibliometric analysis is one of the most used methods in recent years for the review, evaluation and objective representation of the structure within a specific research field (Durieux and Gevenois, 2010; Gutiérrez-Salcedo et al., 2018; Zavařaqi and Fadaie, 2012). Bibliometric variables are frequently used to visualise, from different perspectives, the yield, intellectual structure or scientific cartography of a research field. In this case, they were used to identify and describe the most relevant aspects on the evolution, advances and trends in the field on which this study is focused (Zupic and Cater, 2015); the co-quotation analysis, authorship and co-authorship analysis, co-word analysis, journal analysis and social networking analysis (García-Lillo et al., 2018).

2.2. Data source and sample analysed

The analysed sample consisted of 3148 articles and was obtained from Scopus. The Scopus database is considered the biggest repository of peer reviewed literature, and includes the highest number of articles (70 million) and editors (5,000). It has important tools to visualise, follow and analyze research yield, as well as impact metrics (FECYT, 2019a, 2019b). Peer reviewing is the method used by this multidisciplinary database for the validation of scientific research (Elsevier, 2019). The articles were selected as analysis documents for this study to guarantee the validation process to which they are subject, their quality and validity.

2.3. Main stages of the process

Table 1 describes the three main stages that formed part of the analysis process together with the aspects that were considered for the selection of the sample, the bibliographic database and the software for the construction and graphic representation of the information. Once the main terms used by the researchers in reference to this subject area were identified, the documents obtained were analysed. By combining the different search parameters in the Scopus database, it was confirmed that the "title" field showed more detailed and relevant documents for this study.

2.4. Period and variables analysed

Although the analysis period selected was the 88 years from 1931 to 2018, scientific articles related to agricultural waste were only found for 65 years, therefore this is the total amount of years analysed. This period included the first article

Table 1
Stages of the bibliometric analysis process.

Stages of the process	Selection criteria	Result
1. Search criteria	1.1 Search and analysis of terms used by the researchers to refer to agricultural wastes in databases 2.2 Analysis of the more adequate research field according to the specific issue and approach of the documents obtained. 2.3 Verification and definition of the publication period and typology of documents according to terms and research fields selected.	(TITLE ("agricultur* waste") OR TITLE ("agricultur* residue") OR TITLE ("crop* residue*")) AND DOCTYPE (ar) AND PUBYEAR < 2019
2. Selection of bibliographic databases and documents for the analysis	2.1 Analysis of the amount and typology of the documents contained in the WOS and SCOPUS database	SCOPUS - 3.148 document results
3. Data process, systematization and data analysis	3.1 Assessment of the type of analysis, indicators and adequate tools for scientific mapping (SciMAT, Cit-NetExplorer or VOSViewer)	Indicators and bibliometric maps with VOSViewer: - Document production and authorship - Co-citation of documents - Co-citation of authors - Co-occurrence of keywords - Co-occurrence of terms - Impact factor of journals - Networking maps of relationship between main authors, institutions and countries.

published on this issue in the database until the last article in 2018. This wide selection permitted making a complete analysis on the evolution of field study and a detailed assessment of bibliographic data considering variables such as: the annual number of articles (A), number of authors (AU), number of countries (C), the annual number of citations in total articles (TC), the number of references in total articles (NR), number of journals (J) and the number of institutions (I), as well as, the approaches and trends of the subject field in accordance with the emerging keywords per periods.

2.5. Graphical representation of data

The interactions and interrelationships between authors, countries, as well as the evolution of keywords and term relevance were represented through bibliometric maps that were made with VOSviewer (version 1.6.11., Leiden University, Leiden, The Netherlands), a software widely used for bibliometric cartography because it is specialised in graphic representation and visualisation of big co-quotation and co-occurrence maps, that can be easily interpreted (Van Eck and Waltman, 2010).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Evolution of scientific production

Fig. 1 shows the evolution in the number of articles published and the annual citations and also significant variations within this research field during the whole study period (65 years). It increased from two journals in 1931 to 266 in 2018. It highlighted the growing interest for this issue from 1998, when there was a increase in the number of articles that saw the annual average increased from 23 to 51 for the period indicated (with some small differences across the years). More than half of the total articles (60%) have been published over the last 10 years (2009–2018), with 1888 out of the 3148 articles that were registered for the 65 year period. The average of journals in the decade indicated is 188 articles per year, and 2018 witnessed the highest number of registered journals.

The first significant increase in citations was registered in the year 1960, when the average number of citations increased from 3 per year to 87 for that period. This average was kept low until 1991, when more than 1000 citations were registered, which reduced during the years 1992, 1993 and 1994. In 2008, the highest number of citations (5,963) was reported. The first article published in 1931 is titled “*Winter leaching and the manurial value of green manures and crop residues for winter wheat*” (Crowther and Mirchandani, 1931) and the last article published on this issue in December 2018 is “*Impact of open burning of crop residues on air pollution and climate change in Indonesia*” (Andini et al., 2018), none of them have associated citations.

The article with the highest number of citations (1,137) is from 2004 and the second highest (830) is from 2002 (Table 2). The total number of citations of the 10 articles listed in Table 2 (6279), represent 8% of the total number of citations of the sample.

The main characteristics of articles published on agricultural waste since 1931 to 2018 were analysed in five periods, each period represents 13 years, with the exception of the first and second period, where only the years in which there are

Fig. 1. Total number of articles published and annual citations for 1931–2018 period.

Table 2
Articles with the highest number of citations for 1931–2018 period.

A	AN	TC	Y	J
Global potential bioethanol production from wasted crops and crop residues	Kim, S.; Dale, B.E.	1137	2004	Biomass and Bioenergy
Single- and multi-component adsorption of cadmium and zinc using activated carbon derived from bagasse - An agricultural waste	Mohan, D.; Singh, K.P.	830	2002	Water Research
Isolation and characterisation of nanofibers from agricultural residues - Wheat straw and soy hulls	Alemdar, A; Sain, M.	764	2008	Bioresource Technology
The forms of alkalis in the biochar produced from crop residues at different temperatures	Yuan, J.-H.; Xu, R.-K.; Zhang, H.	655	2011	Bioresource Technology
Compositions and sorptive properties of crop residue-derived chars	Chun, Y.; Sheng, G.; Chiou, G.T.; Xing, B.	610	2004	Environmental Science and Technology
Physical removal of textile dyes from effluents and solid-state fermentation of dye-adsorbed agricultural residues	Nigam, P.; Armour, G.; Banat, I.M.; Singh, D.; Marchant, R.	502	2000	Bioresource Technology
World crop residues production and implications of its use as a biofuel	Lal, R.	475	2005	Environment International
Batch adsorption of methylene blue from aqueous solution by garlic peel, an agricultural waste biomass	Hameed, B.H.; Ahmad, A.A.	436	2009	Journal of Hazardous Materials
Effects of temperature and particle size on bio-char yield from pyrolysis of agricultural residues	Demirbas, A.	435	2004	Journal of Analytical and Applied Pyrolysis
Utilisation of various agricultural wastes for activated carbon preparation and application for the removal of dyes and metal ions from aqueous solutions	Kadirvelu, K.; Kavipriya, M.; Karthika, C.; (...), Vennilamani, N.; Pattabhi, S.	435	2003	Bioresource Technology

A: article name; AN: name of authors; TC: total number of citations; Y: year of publication of the article; J: name of journals.

publications are shown (Table 3). Over the first 13 years, the first period assessed (1931–1965), 18 articles were published that represent only 1% compared with the total number of journals. The average for this period was one article per year.

For the second period (1966–1979) the number of articles published increased six times (104 articles), with an annual average of eight journals. The articles published increased more than doubled in the third period (1980–1992). In the fourth period (1993–2005), an average of 47 documents were registered annually, which reached 165 articles per year for the last period (2006–2018). The total number of articles published in this period represents only 68% of the journals of the whole period analysed.

The increase is proportional to all the associated variables that were assessed, for example, the number of authors grew from 37, in the first period (1931–1965), with an average of two authors per article, to 6170 in the last period (2006–2018), although without a significant variation in the average number of authors (three per article). This is due to the significant increase in the number of articles published in the last period. More than 70% of the authors of scientific production analysed are concentrated in the last 13 years. These authors come from different countries that, compared with the collaboration figures increase between periods, although they are not so significant as for other analysed variables. Therefore, for the first 13 years, the participation was registered in articles from four countries, this amount increased by 90% in the third period (1980–1992), and reached 110 countries in the last 13 years.

According to the number of documents that were considered by the authors of the analysed publications, to reinforce and support their research, 242 references (NR) were registered for the second period (1966–1979), an average of two references per document. This amount increased exponentially for the other periods, up to an average of 28 references per document for the last period (2006–2018). This evolution is opposite to the evolution of citations (TC), an indicator that allows us to know the number of times they were mentioned as a reference for other documents. Citations showed variations in the different periods. Thus, the average number of citations in the first period, 1931–1965, was 8.3, while in the next period it decreased to 6.7 citations per document. The fourth period (1993–2005), registered the highest average of citations per document for the whole 65 years, with a total of 27,402, this amount (45.1) is lower than the amount registered for the last period (2006–2018), when the average number of citations per document more than halved (19.9).

Finally, the number of journals where the articles were published, which was 11 for the first period, increased significantly (135) for the third period (1980–1992), it reached 742 journals for the last 13 years. The number of institutions linked to the

Table 3
Main characteristics of publications in 1931–2018 period.

Period	A	NR	AU	C	TC	TC/A	J	I
1931–1965	18	*	37	4	150	8.3	11	17
1966–1979	104	242	181	13	693	6.7	62	41
1980–1992	270	2761	536	40	5769	21.4	135	274
1993–2005	607	12994	1503	70	27402	45.1	269	1008
2006–2018	2149	60774	6170	110	42715	19.9	742	4731

A: the annual number of articles; NR: the number of references in total articles. AU: number of authors; C: number of countries; TC: the annual number of citations in total articles; J: number of journals; I: Number of Institutions. *Not available information.

articles also showed an important periodic increase, from 17 organisations interested in the issue in the first 13 years (1931–1965) to 4731 in the last 13 years.

At first sight, the titles of the articles mentioned and enumerated, as well as the growing periodic figures of articles, authors, institutions and journals, provides an insight into the growing importance of the issue of agricultural wastes.

3.2. Productivity of authors, countries and institutions

Table 4 shows the main characteristics of authorship of the publication of scientific production on agricultural waste from 1931 to 2018. It must be highlighted that four of the top ten prolific authors are Chinese. In first position, was Guangming Zeng, a researcher and professor of the Faculty of Science and Environmental Engineering, Hunan University, Changsha. He has focused on waste recycling, cleaner production techniques and environmental systems engineering (HNU, 2019). Of the 20 articles published by this author, his main article on this issue has 177 citations (Gao et al., 2008). This author also has the highest H index and the second highest number of total citations.

In second place, with 17 articles and 446 associated citations, we find the author Jiachao Zhang, affiliated to the School of Resources and Environment in Hunan Agricultural University, an important Innovation and Research Centre in new rural development (HUNAU, 2019). The main article of this author on this issue registered 132 citations (Zhang et al., 2011). Within the authors, Sylvie Recous, registered the highest average number of citations per article (64). Two of her 12 articles (Trinsoutrot et al., 2000; Nicolardot et al., 2001) have a 65% of the total citations for this author (768).

André Babou Bationo with 11 associated documents and 534 citations was the first of the 10 enumerated authors who published the first article on this issue (Bationo and Mokwunye, 1991), and registered 125 citations. Man Yu, who has 12 associated articles with 364 citations, is the author with the most recent article, which was published in December 2018 (Ren et al., 2018) and has 4 registered citations. Likewise, in August 2018, an article was published on this issue, whose authors were three of the researchers listed in Table 4 (Guangming Zeng, Jiachao Zhang and Yaoning Chen) (Zhang et al., 2018), which demonstrates the interaction and cooperation between some authors, mainly those of the same nationality and/or those who share the same institutional affiliation.

Although China is the country with the highest representation within the 10 main authors ranking, the United States is the country with the highest scientific production on agricultural waste, 17% of the total published articles come from that country (Fig. 2).

During the first four periods indicated (Table 5), the United States is placed first within the most prolific countries followed by India, which published 513 articles, 16% of the sample. This is related with the high number of citations for these two countries, United States (17,796) and India (12,976). In the last period (2006–2018), India was placed first, China second and the United States third. Although the United States kept a significant number of articles (271), which represents 51% of the total articles (528). China is in third place with 377 documents and 7987 citations.

Brazil is the other country in the last period (2006–2018) with the largest increase in its scientific production on this issue. Brazil is the only country in South America which belongs to the 10 countries ranking, it is placed fourth in the table with 148 articles and 1869 associated citations. 88% of its articles were published in the last period. Canada is highlighted because although has a relatively low number of publications (144) it has the second highest average number of citations (31.23).

According to data from presented by the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, UNESCO, in the "UNESCO Science Report 2010 - The current status of science around the world" (UNESCO, 2010), the significant increase of scientific articles on this issue in recent years can be associated with the increase in world investment in R + D. Consequently, there is a higher number of researchers. The proportion of researchers from developing countries increased from 30% in 2002 to 38% in 2007, and China is the country which registered the largest increase in researchers (UN, 2010). For this reason, this country has experienced a significant boom with respect to the number of articles in the last 13 years.

Likewise, UNESCO in "Science report - Towards 2030", published in 2015 (UN, 2015a), stated that the USA still dominates the field, with 28% of global investment in R&D. China has moved into second place (20%), ahead of the European Union (19%). This trend could be a key factor in the evolution and strengthening of this research field because the largest scientific

Table 4
Authors with highest production of articles on agricultural waste in the 1931–2018 period.

Authors	A	TC	TC/A	Institution	C	1st A	Last A	H index
Zeng, G.	20	758	37.90	Hunan University	China	2007	2018	15
Zhang, J.	17	446	26.24	Hunan Agricultural University	China	2010	2018	11
Daughtry, C.S.T.	15	632	42.13	USDA ARS Beltsville Agricultural Research Centre	United States	1993	2016	12
De Neve, S.	15	539	35.93	Universiteit Gent	Belgium	1996	2017	11
Bhatti, H.N.	13	255	19.62	University of Agriculture, Faisalabad	Pakistan	2010	2016	9
Chen, Y.	13	389	29.92	Hunan University	China	2010	2018	10
Hofman, G.	13	527	40.54	Universiteit Gent	Belgium	1996	2010	11
Recous, S.	12	768	64.00	INRA Institut National de La Recherche Agronomique	France	2000	2017	11
Yu, M.	12	364	30.33	Zhejiang Academy of Agricultural Sciences	China	2009	2018	8
Bationo, A.	11	534	48.55	International Fertilizer Development Centre - IFDC	Ghana	1991	2016	8

A: number of articles; TC: number of citations for all articles; TC/A: number of citations by article; C: country.

Fig. 2. Countries with higher scientific production for 1931–2018 period.

Table 5

Countries with higher number of articles in the 1931–2018 period.

Country	A	TC	TC/A	H index	R(A)				
					1931–1965	1966–1979	1980–1992	1993–2005	2006–2018
United states	528	17796	33.70	62	1(13)	1(19)	1(66)	1(159)	3(271)
India	513	12976	25.29	60	2(1)	2(4)	2(34)	2(92)	1(382)
China	377	7987	21.19	45	0	0	22(1)	10(16)	2(360)
Brazil	148	1869	12.63	24	0	0	21(1)	9(17)	4(130)
Canada	144	4497	31.23	36	0	3(3)	4(15)	3(43)	5(83)
Spain	106	2462	23.23	29	0	0	15(3)	7(22)	6(81)
Australia	94	2196	23.36	26	0	7(1)	3(18)	14(14)	12(61)
United kingdom	93	2779	29.88	28	4(1)	0	6(7)	4(35)	17(50)
Egypt	92	1506	16.37	20	0	4(2)	8(5)	11(16)	8(69)
Italy	88	1932	21.95	22	0	0	5(7)	13(15)	11(66)

A: number of articles; TC: number of citations for all articles; TC/A: number of citations by article. R: rank position by number of articles.

production in recent years have been generated in countries whose financial investment has been bigger. Furthermore, this report also points out that other emerging countries from Latin America, such as Brazil and Mexico, have also increased their investments in R + D and that the most important scientific disciplines in Brazil are agriculture and biological sciences, which could explain their important contribution on this issue.

It is also interesting to note that the largest increase in the number of publications in Brazil (1993), coincides with the year in which a regulation forced a major use of biofuels, causing a higher demand for bioethanol. This fuel would be extracted from sugarcane, mainly through juice fermentation and blending with molasses (FAO, 2008b; Hassan and Abul Kalam, 2013). In addition, the resulting molasses could be distilled and rectified to obtain hydrated ethanol and, after a dehydration process, anhydrous ethanol could be obtained (BNDES and CGEE, 2008). With respect to the main collaborations between countries for the publication of research works, United Kingdom is in first place with 45.2% followed by Australia with 44.7%. Spain is in third place, with 106 articles in total, 43 out of these articles have been made in collaboration with other 20 countries (Table 6). The United States, although had the collaboration of a higher number of countries, only published 144 articles in collaboration with other countries out of the 528 articles published. The lowest collaboration percentage is reported for India, even though it registers the second highest number of countries associated in the articles (34).

It should be highlighted that there is no any direct inter-relationship between the number of citations and the articles with international co-authorship. The articles have different percentages of citations that does not vary depending on collaborations. The United States and China are the main collaborators with higher numbers of articles. The main collaborators with Spain are countries from Latin America (Chile, Brazil and Mexico), which shows the interaction and inter-relationship between these countries.

eight European countries and three American countries (South and North), which confirms the higher interaction between these two continents in relation with scientific production on agricultural wastes.

Europe has an important representation in this collaboration network because it has the highest number of countries (13), followed by Asia (9) and Africa (5). Europe's participation is led by Spain and Italy, with the highest contribution (194 articles), this participation highlights not only the amount of countries that comprise the network, but also interaction and collaboration with the other continents, which is reflected when integrating all the clusters represented.

In relation to the institutions that have participated in the publication of scientific production on agricultural waste, the United States is in first place because its main representative is the United States Department of Agriculture, USDA, which has contributed 182 articles, 34% of the total articles that come from that country (528), and 6% of the total articles of the total sample (Table 7). 105 articles out of the 182 come from the main in-house research agency of the USDA, the Agricultural Research Service (ARS), who have published 105 articles and the highest H index (33) and the second highest average of citations per document (43.15). The remaining 77 articles, which also have the second highest registration of citations (3,061), correspond with other research centres belonging to the USDA.

China's participation is also important, with three institutions that have contributed 170 articles, which amounts to 5% of the total sample. These three institutions are public (two of them are academic and the other one is a government department). The Chinese Academy of Sciences, CAS, is the most important, ranking second place with 90 articles and 2601 citations.

The INRA, the Institut National de La Recherche Agronomique in France, is placed in 9th position in the table, with 35 articles published and has the highest average of citations per article (45.37) and the second highest percentage of publications with international co-authorship. Likewise, the Wageningen University and Research Centre of the Netherlands, has contributed with 41 articles, 68.3% of them have been published in collaboration with other institutions. The ten institutions that are listed have contributed 18% of the total analysed articles. It is important to highlight that the type of institutions and the sector are all public, three are governmental bodies, three academic institutions (universities and institutes), two research centres and one is a research centre and university simultaneously, all of them are specialised in agricultural sciences.

3.3. Distribution of scientific production by subject categories and journals

The evolution of the subject categories within the study of agricultural waste has been changing over the last 65 years. Agricultural and Biological Sciences is the dominant category, in which 1053 articles of the total sample are included (Fig. 4). This category occupied the first position throughout the whole period analysed, except for the second period, in which it was moved down by engineering to fourth position. Environmental Sciences, which occupied fifth position in the first period (1931–1965), with only one article, was the second subject category from the second period (1966–1979), with a notable number of articles (1,053), which represented 19% of the published articles (see Figs. 6, 7, 8 and 5).

In relation with these two subject categories, it is important to highlight that from the fourth period (1993–2005) to the fifth period (2006–2018), the highest increase in the number of articles associated with these categories saw a move from 364 in the fourth period to 895 in the last period for the first subject category, and from 150 to 801 for the second category. This means that 76% of the articles belonging to Environmental Sciences and 64% of Agricultural and Biological Sciences have been published in the last 13 years.

The subject category Chemical Engineering occupies third position, and groups 9% of published articles. In fourth and fifth position, with the same percentage (7%) Energy and Engineering categories are found, with 393 and 375 associated documents respectively. These five categories group 3694 articles, an amount higher than the total sample of analysed articles (3,148), this is because this research category incorporates several disciplines that have different perspectives of analysis; therefore, its classification cannot be grouped in only one category. The rest of subject categories group a total of 1764 articles, 56% of the total articles analysed. All the articles of the sample are grouped in 25 of the 27 main subject categories of Scopus (Elsevier, 2017).

Table 7

Main institutions according to the number of articles from 1931 to 2018.

Institution	C	A	TC	TC/A	H index	IC (%)	TCIC	TCNIC
USDA Agricultural Research Service, Washington DC	United States	105	4531	43.15	33	12.4%	12.46	47.49
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	90	2601	28.90	25	35.6%	43.25	20.98
United States Department of Agriculture	United States	77	3061	39.75	29	10.4%	20.75	41.96
Agriculture et Agroalimentaire Canada	Canada	59	2036	34.51	28	18.6%	14.18	39.17
Ministry of Education China	China	51	793	15.55	18	23.5%	10.17	17.21
Wageningen University and Research Centre	Netherlands	41	1014	24.73	20	68.3%	21.43	31.85
National Research Centre	Egypt	40	810	20.25	14	30.0%	12.67	23.50
ICAR - Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi	India	37	367	9.92	11	10.8%	6.50	10.33
INRA Institut National de La Recherche Agronomique	France	35	1588	45.37	19	51.4%	27.28	64.53
Hunan University	China	29	821	28.31	16	6.9%	50.50	26.67

C: country; A: number of articles; TC: number of citations for all articles; TC/A: number of citations by article; IC: percentage of articles made with international collaboration; TCIC: number of citations by article made with international collaboration; TCNIC: number of citations by article made without international collaboration.

Fig. 4. Comparison between the growing trends of the subject categories in agricultural waste research, from 1931 to 2018.

Fig. 5. Keyword network based on co-occurrence for the 1966–1979 period.

The subject categories define the articles in different journals that have special interest on this research issue, although from different points of view. Table 8 shows the 25 main journals that, during the period assessed (1931–2018), have published the scientific production under analysis. A total of 1006 journals have published the 3148 articles analysed on agricultural waste and, in the last 13 years, the number of journals interested in this issue has increased considerably. In the first 13 years (1931–1965), only 11 journals published the scientific production of that period (18 articles). For the second period (1966–1979), 51 journals were added to the list, such that 104 articles of that period were published in 62 journals.

In the third period (1980–1992) 135 journals were counted. In the fourth period (1993–2005) the increase was almost doubled, 269 journals published 607 articles in that period. In the last period, from 2006 to 2018, 742 journals published the 2148 articles produced, which was 74% of the total number of journals. 45% of the journals belong to the Netherlands, 30% to the United States and only 5% of the journals come from South America. 65% of the journals come from Europe.

A high percentage of the journals (83%) belong to the Q1 quartile, according to 2018 SCImago Journal Rank (SJR) indicators. Only four of the main journals belong to the second and third quartiles. The first article of the sample analysed was published in the journal "The Journal of Agricultural Science", whose specialty is Agricultural and Biological Sciences, Agronomy and Crop Sciences. This journal only accumulates a total of four published articles during the whole analysed period. The most recent article of the sample (December 2018), was published in the journal Current Science, whose subject category is multidisciplinary. This journal accumulates five articles of the total sample.

The "Bioresource Technology" journal has published the highest number of articles (98), which represents 3% of the total sample and places it in first position within the ranking. Furthermore, this journal has the highest number of total citations

Fig. 6. Keyword network based on co-occurrence for 1980–1992 period.

(6,643), and it appeared for the first time in the third period (1980–1992) in the 17th position in the journal list. It increased from three to 25 articles in the fourth period (1993–2005) and published 70 in the last period (2006–2018), therefore, it occupied the first position of the list in those last two periods. The first article of this journal, dated 1991, only has one associated citation (Gibbons et al., 1991).

The second journal with the highest number of articles (48) is “Soil Science Society of America Journal”, which specialises in Agricultural, Biological and Soil Sciences. This journal has a total of 2670 citations and an H index of 147. Biomass and Bioenergy Journal, with 47 documents (3032 citations), is placed in third position in the ranking. This journal, with an H index of 156, has Agricultural, Biological and Soil Sciences among its main subject categories. This journal has a total of 2670 citations and a H index of 147. Biomass and Bioenergy journal, with 47 documents (3032 citations), is placed in third position in the ranking. This journal with an H index of 156, has among its main subject categories: Agricultural and Biological Sciences, Agronomy and Crop Sciences, Renewable Energy, Sustainability and Environment and Waste Management and Elimination. The article with the highest number of citations of all the sample analysed, dated from 2004, was published in this journal (1137 citations).

The Journal of Hazardous Materials, which has 28 documents published on this issue, has the second total highest number of citations (3,933) and an average of 140.46 citations per document - the highest in the list. Among the main areas and subject categories of this journal, we find Environmental Sciences and Waste Management and Elimination. 23% of the total number of articles published on agricultural waste were published in these 25 journals.

The number of journals, as well as their evolution throughout the different periods confirms the growing importance of this issue for researchers and institutions, and also draws attention to the representatives and/or responsible persons in the media through which these articles are visualised and diffused. Good interaction and communication between scientists and society is an important support tool for research. For more than 4 decades, journals have been an important indicator for impact assessments of research studies, which are mainly considered through the number of citations (Garfield, 1979, 1998).

It is also important to highlight that journals in recent years have passed from having a specialised approach in one or few disciplines to a wider framework, which is multidisciplinary and gives more opportunities for dissemination within the scientific community (Ackerson and Chapman, 2003). In fact, one of the 27 subject categories of Scopus are “General Matter”

Fig. 7. Keyword network based on co-occurrence for 1993–2005 period.

which includes multidisciplinary journals. This is also visible in the wide range of specific subject categories in which the journals are grouped, which has increased over the last years, from 295 in 2012 to 313 in 2018 (SJR, 2019).

3.4. Keywords analysis

The first keyword analysis was made taking into account maps based on literature for each of the periods. These word co-occurrence maps reflect the main terms that have been selected by the authors and by the Scopus database managers (Van Eck and Waltman, 2014). The items that form part of the network maps were selected by (VOSviewer) software, according to the number of occurrences (minimum five) and the strength that exist between terms, indicating and representing the strongest links through lines and different colour groups (cluster) (Van Eck and Waltman, 2011).

The terms that were part of the search were not included among the keywords, nor were some indexing terms (Indexed keywords), added by Scopus to the records. Thus, the list of keywords includes the keywords defined by the authors, such as those added by Elsevier's bibliometric thesaurus, called EMTREE, which contains more than 65,000 keywords on life sciences, health sciences and other topics unique to the Embase database (Cañedo Andalia et al., 2015; Elsevier, 2017).

For the 18 documents of the first period (1931–1965), the author keywords are not registered, only two keywords indexed by EMTREE: "article" and "water pollution" are indicated. For the second period (1966–1979) the following terms are highlighted: "agricultural engineering", "waste management" and "environmental health". These two large clusters reveal the structure of 104 studies of this period. The first and most important cluster, with 17 terms (red), indicates the different uses and/or benefits obtained from the use of harvest waste mainly wheat straw, animal food, adequate waste management, and reduction and improvement of environmental conditions.

In this cluster, United States appears within the first terms, because it is the country where more studies were performed, 18% of the total articles of the period. Likewise, it is important to highlight that in 1960, United States was among the three main wheat exporter countries, and the studies of this period were focused mainly on this crop (FAO, 1960). The second cluster (green) indicates some of the main physical-chemical processes analysed for the waste utilisation, especially for transformation into by-products.

Table 8
Main journals that published articles from 1931 to 2018.

Journal	A	TC	TC/A	Hi (A)	Hi (J)	SJR	C	R (A)				
								1931 –1965	1966 –1979	1980 –1992	1993 –2005	2006 –2018
Bioresource Technology	98	6643	67.79	41	251	2.157(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	17(3)	1(25)	1(70)
Soil Science Society of America Journal	48	2670	55.63	32	147	2.16(Q1)	United States	0	0	2(16)	2(18)	24(14)
Biomass and Bioenergy	47	3032	64.51	24	156	1.072(Q1)	United Kingdom	0	0	58(1)	5(11)	2(35)
Soil and Tillage Research	40	2095	52.38	24	117	1.898(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	6(8)	4(13)	10(19)
Plant and Soil	38	1358	35.74	21	163	1.187 (Q1)	Netherlands	10(1)	0	3(10)	8(10)	17(17)
Biology and Fertility of Soils	37	1199	32.41	20	109	1.187 (Q1)	Germany	0	0	11(4)	3(16)	15(17)
Soil Biology and Biochemistry	33	1465	44.39	23	186	2.448(Q1)	United Kingdom	0	0	22(3)	6(11)	11(19)
Journal of Hazardous Materials	28	3933	140.46	27	235	1.958(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	0	92(2)	4(26)
Agronomy Journal	27	854	31.63	14	113	1.049(Q1)	United States	0	0	0	7(10)	14(17)
Communications in Soil Science and Plant Analysis	27	202	7.48	8	59	0.307(Q3)	United States	0	0	0	10(9)	12(18)
Desalination and Water Treatment	27	162	6.00	9	45	0.377(Q2)	United States	0	0	0	0	3(27)
Nutrient Cycling in Agroecosystems	24	554	23.08	14	87	1.060(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	0	12(9)	21(15)
Waste Management	24	993	41.38	17	127	1.523(Q1)	United Kingdom	0	0	128(1)	104(2)	6(21)
Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry	23	677	29.43	13	262	1.111(Q1)	United States	3(2)	0	19(3)	19(6)	29(12)
Atmospheric Environment	22	574	26.09	14	211	1.418(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	0	129(1)	5(21)
Soil Use and Management	22	806	36.64	11	69	0.753(Q1)	United States	0	0	119(1)	17(7)	25(14)
Field Crops Research	21	734	34.95	14	127	1.703(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	75(1)	11(9)	36(11)
Industrial Crops and Products	20	578	28.90	14	103	1.015(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	0	182(1)	8(19)
Journal of Cleaner Production	20	216	10.80	11	150	1.620(Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	0	0	7(20)
Revista Brasileira de Ciencia do Solo	20	283	14.15	9	44	0.510(Q2)	Brazil	0	0	0	244(1)	9(19)
Agricultural Wastes	19	290	15.26	7	–	–	–	0	0	1(19)	0	0
Agriculture Ecosystems And Environment	19	560	29.47	12	151	1.54 (Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	15(3)	30(4)	28(12)
Journal Of Analytical And Applied Pyrolysis	19	1144	60.21	13	115	1.11 (Q1)	Netherlands	0	0	0	191(1)	13(18)
Journal Of Soil And Water Conservation	18	279	15.50	9	66	0.73(Q1)	United States	0	1(6)	0	95(2)	44(10)
Applied Biochemistry And Biotechnology	17	468	27.53	12	97	0.61 (Q2)	United States	0	0	28(2)	125(1)	22(14)

A: number of articles; R: rank position by number of articles; TC: number of citations for all articles; TC/A: number of citations by article; Hi(A): H index articles; Hi(J): H index journal; SJR: Scimago Journal Rank (quartile); C: country.

Canada was in first position in cereal production (wheat and rice) within North America countries. In 1992, world cereal production increased by 4.2% compared with the previous year (FAO, 1993).

The second cluster (green) groups 68 terms (some strongly represented such as “carbon” “temperature” “pH” and “adsorption”), properties and physical and chemical processes that have a main role during the transformation process of harvest wastes or on the soil when they are added after the process to increase productivity. The third group (blue) with 39 terms, reflects elements, chemical substances (cellulose, lignin) and microorganisms (bacteria, fungi), which are essential in the biochemical processes of transformation of organic matter, among them, fermentation is cited. The other groups also reflect terms associated with those described, which allows us to know some of the main approaches of the studies related to variables, elements, compounds, methods and objectives of the use processes, transformation and/or utilisation of agricultural wastes.

The map of the last period (2006–2018), represents a lower number of cluster (5), but each one has a higher amount of terms. In the main group, with 228 terms (red), once again items from the main compounds are highlighted, such as “cellulose”, “lignin” and essential chemical reactions (fermentation, enzymatic activity) for the processes of transformation of plant remains from harvests. The second group with 207 terms (green) groups the main analysis units throughout the whole period, that is, the type of crops, cereals, mainly (maize and wheat) and soil. The third group (blue) with 204 terms, in a similar way, highlights physical, chemical and biological characteristics of the agricultural by-products that are subject to transformation and utilisation. After the highest term in the fourth group (light green), “*Triticum aestivum*”, the term “Biomass”, is the term with the second highest number of occurrences in the entire network (305 articles).

Similarly, in this period, China appears as an emerging country. China, together with Brazil, occupied the second and third positions respectively as the largest maize producers in 2000 and 2002 (FAO, 2003). In 2012, according to a FAO's report, Asia reached an unprecedented volume of maize production, with China as the main producer (FAO, 2012). Additionally, it should be pointed out that in this group, the main items give a special relevance to environmental issues, including “Sustainable Development”, “Renewable Resources”, “Alternative Energies”, “Climate Change”, “Emission Inventory” and “Sustainability”, that considerably increase their inclusion in the studies and others that emerged exclusively in this last period.

Table 9 shows the 20 most used keywords in the 3148 articles on agricultural waste over the whole assessed period (1931–2018). The analysis considered the importance and evolution of keywords according to the number of documents that

Table 9

Main keywords in the 1931–2018 period.

Keyword	1931–2018		1931–1965		1966–1979		1980–1992		1993–2005		2006–2018	
	R (A)	%	R (A)	%	R (A)	%	R (A)	%	R (A)	%	R (A)	%
<i>Zea mays</i>	412	13.1%	0	0.0%	65(3)	2.9%	14(17)	6.3%	6(82)	13.5%	7(310)	14.4%
<i>Triticum aestivum</i>	409	13.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	17(12)	4.4%	5(84)	13.8%	6(313)	14.6%
Biomass	378	12.0%	0	0.0%	73(2)	1.9%	22(9)	3.3%	10(62)	10.2%	8(305)	14.2%
Adsorption	276	8.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	15(40)	6.6%	10(235)	10.9%
Carbon	231	7.3%	0	0.0%	75(2)	1.9%	81(3)	1.1%	12(54)	8.9%	14(172)	8.0%
Nitrogen	232	7.4%	0	0.0%	59(3)	2.9%	31(6)	2.2%	8(70)	11.5%	18(153)	7.1%
Cellulose	218	6.9%	0	0.0%	147(1)	1.0%	39(5)	1.9%	28(27)	4.4%	13(185)	8.6%
Maize	213	6.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	59(4)	1.5%	24(31)	5.1%	11(178)	8.3%
Wheat	200	6.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	48(5)	1.9%	20(37)	6.1%	16(158)	7.4%
Straw	194	6.2%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	33(6)	2.2%	29(27)	4.4%	15(160)	7.4%
Ph	170	5.4%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	32(26)	4.3%	20(142)	6.6%
Soils	173	5.5%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	15(16)	5.9%	25(31)	5.1%	25(125)	5.8%
Fermentation	164	5.2%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	18(11)	4.1%	37(22)	3.6%	23(131)	6.1%
Waste management	161	5.1%	0	0.0%	3(14)	13.5%	3(39)	14.4%	21(33)	5.4%	70(75)	3.5%
Chemistry	160	5.1%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	70(15)	2.5%	21(144)	6.7%
Lignin	151	4.8%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	27(7)	2.6%	38(22)	3.6%	26(122)	5.7%
Soil	149	4.7%	0	0.0%	43(4)	3.8%	32(6)	2.2%	19(37)	6.1%	33(102)	4.7%
Temperature	146	4.6%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	33(26)	4.3%	27(118)	5.5%
Kinetics	142	4.5%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	56(17)	2.8%	24(125)	5.8%
Decomposition	141	4.5%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%	149(2)	0.7%	13(45)	7.4%	36(94)	4.4%

A: number of articles; R: rank position; %: percentage of articles in which it appears.

included both the term and the ranking attained in each period. The term *Zea mays* was consolidated as the most important for the whole period, with 412 occurrences (13% of the total documents). This keyword appeared for the first time, in three documents in the second period (1966–1979), with a 65th ranking position, and it maintained that ranking until the last period (2006–2018) when, with 310 documents, it occupied 7th position.

In second place, with 409 associated articles, the term *Triticum aestivum* is found. It appeared for the first time in the third period (1980–1992) in 12 documents, and it increased its frequency significantly in the last period (2006–2018) to 313 documents, which represented 77% of the total documents in which it is included. Biomass was included in a total of 378 documents, which places it in third position. In the second period (1966–1979), it appeared for the first time among the last positions of the list, with only two documents, but in the fourth period (1993–2005) it occupied the tenth position with 62 documents. It reached its peak in the last 13 years, when 305 documents included this term (81% of the total).

Fig. 9 provides a detailed analysis of the semantic structure of the articles and represents the co-occurrence map of the terms contained in the titles and abstracts of the 972 documents in which the three main words of Table 8 are included, that is, 31% of the total analysed articles. This map represents a complementary analysis that, unlike the keyword maps, analyses a larger amount of text data and assesses the relevance of terms rather than the frequency, which is used with keywords co-occurrence.

The two big clusters, which are formed in relation to biomass and cereal crop wastes such as maize and wheat, reflect some of the main methods, techniques, variables and unit analysis that were already identified in previous maps. The main group (red) indicates how the studies emphasize the transformation of agricultural wastes, mainly for the production of by-products or bioproducts (biofuels, additives, chemical substances, food) that are different due to their properties and uses in different fields. The terms “process” and “analysis” indicate how studies prioritize the process of organic matter through physical-chemical methods, which imply the presence of some compounds, reactions and techniques, which are identified clearly in the network. Rice straw is the other cereal waste highlighted in this group.

In the second group, soil is given priority again as study unit. As was mentioned, the analysis is focused on assessing the effects of the incorporation of agricultural wastes processed on this substrate, using techniques as farming work. In the studies, different types of crops are considered, mainly cereals, for which different techniques were implemented, therefore, the term “system” was used repeatedly.

Fig. 10 represents the network map, from 2006 to 2014, of the total keywords included in the analysed studies over the 65 years, which allows for a more detailed visualisation of its evolution. In relation to the different variables identified in the maps, it can be observed that the focus during the earlier years was on transforming waste for the production of organic fertilizer, as a nutrient for the soil fertilization and to use it as bovine and ovine food. In turn, these animal excrements were used as appropriate components to combine with vegetal organic matter. In this first stage, United States consolidates as the most important country.

Between 2008 and 2010, new concepts arose for the definition of harvest vegetal wastes such as “Biomass”. Wheat crop has a leading role as a waste liable to be used and as system it benefited from the addition of fertilizers derived from processed agricultural wastes. In this period, India was placed as the leading country. Likewise, the transformation methods are more marked for agricultural wastes oriented towards chemical processes and reactions used for obtaining biofuels. These techniques and priorities in the production of bioproducts and bioenergy from harvest wastes are more relevant in the last years

processes for obtaining biofuels and bioenergy, which demand greater technological development. The progress in research is clearly linked to new national policies that, mainly since 2010, have been adjusted to the framework of global governance on sustainable development (Dietz et al., 2018). This new framework is based on a low-carbon economy, replacing fossil fuels with renewable biological resources like agricultural biomass (McCormick and Kautto, 2013; EC, 2017a), allowing the progress of renewable energy to mitigate climate change and achieve the Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), adopted in 2015 (Ciegis et al., 2009).

The strategy of this new model, which is based on the circular economy and the bioeconomy, has promoted the development of studies and research on the identification of techniques and alternatives that allow the efficient management of resources to maximize the useful life of materials and products (Blomsma and Brennan, 2017; Molina-Moreno et al., 2017). However, the development of the bioeconomy has not been limited only to the formulation of local policies; other stakeholders of the society, such as global research networks, have contributed to the increase in the number of initiatives on this new and important economic model (Plaza-Úbeda et al., 2011).

Of the top ten countries with the greatest number of publications in the period 1931–2018, nine have made advances in the definition and implementation of bioeconomic policies and strategies (Table 10). These nine countries are part of the group of 50 countries that, at the global level, have implemented national bioeconomic policies and strategies, according to the report of the German Council on Bioeconomics for the year 2018 (Fund et al., 2018). Although Egypt has contributed significantly to research on agricultural residues (92 articles), it is not in the group of 50, i.e., there is no evidence that Egypt has developed any policy in the field of bioeconomics. In relation to the management instruments presented in Table 10, it is important to highlight that China, the United Kingdom and Australia are the countries with the greatest number of regulations and strategies related to the bioeconomy. On the other hand, the United Kingdom and Brazil were the first to develop policies related to this subject, starting in 2007.

China, which is listed as one of the countries with the greatest contribution in research related to agricultural residues in the last 13 years, is one of the countries that strongly promotes the development of biotechnology, as an essential strategy of the bioeconomy (Fund et al., 2018). All of the countries cited have been evolving in their specific strategies on bioeconomic policy, and they are defining activities to measure and monitoring the technologies used, the biological-based products and services obtained and the impacts in the economic, social and environmental fields (Fund et al., 2018). Furthermore, it is important to highlight that, within the framework of the bioeconomy, public policies have promoted the production of biofuels. Most of the countries in Table 10 are part of the countries of the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), in which many funds have been assigned to subsidize the production and consumption of biofuels. In 2008, Brazil and the United States were the main ethanol producers (90% of world production), followed by Canada, China, India and others. This factor, combined with the importance that bioenergy has acquired, is considered as a possible cause of the increase in research on agricultural residues in the last 10 years and the articulation and collaboration between countries listed in Table 1 (FAO, 2008b). China and India, for example, are focusing their bioeconomy policies on industrial and high-tech innovation (Fund et al., 2018).

Nearly all of the countries listed and their main partners indicated in Table 6 are characterized by high income and big agricultural industries, which generate a bigger production of waste. Consequently, the efficient management of these wastes becomes more relevant. For this reason, countries such as China and other member states of the European Union, thanks to their bioeconomic policies, have made progress in modernizing waste management systems and have obtained high recycling rates in recent years. It should also be noted that in other countries, such as France, Italy and the Netherlands, inter-municipal cooperation and coordination is part of the waste management model, due to the operational objectives, guidelines and common legislative frameworks of the European Union. Other countries, such as Brazil, have made progress in the approval of comprehensive national solid waste policies, which contribute to the reduction of waste generation and promote its reuse and recycling (Kaza et al., 2018).

4. Conclusions

The analysis conducted of the existing scientific production on agricultural wastes in the biggest bibliographic database (Scopus), permits determining that it is an issue with a long trajectory because the first article of worldwide interest was published more than eight decades ago. A high number of countries participated, but above all, the increase in the number of articles is significant over the last 13 years, because more than a half of the articles analysed were published between 2006 and 2018. The ten countries with the highest number of articles on agricultural wastes, 69% of the total articles, have published more than 50% of these articles in the last 13 years.

The top ten countries published 2183 articles, 41% come from Asia and 31% come from North America. United States is clearly the leading researcher on agricultural wastes and, together with India, they have continually contributed an important number of scientific articles over the 65 years assessed. China is in third position, it provided 12% of the total articles, and 95% of these articles were published in the last 13 years, which shows that China is an emerging country in research on this field.

These three countries have historically led the lists of the main world producers of cereals, mainly wheat and maize. These crops have been the main focus of the research on agricultural wastes. 39% of the total articles focused their analysis in the use of wastes coming from these types of crops and/or the effect of the addition of biomass on soils with these types of crops.

The top ten researchers on this issue have contributed 141 articles that represent only 4% of the total production analysed and 7% of the total citations, a low percentage that indicates the multiplicity and variety of authors that have focused their

Table 10
Main policies and strategies on bioeconomy by country.

Country	Perspective	Document Name
United states	Bioenergy & Bioproducts	Strategic Plan for a Thriving and Sustainable Bioeconomy (2016)
	Research & Innovation	Strategy for American Innovation (2015)
	Agriculture	The Farm Bill (2014)
	Holistic Bioeconomy Development	The Bioeconomy Blueprint (2012)
India	High-Tech	National Biotechnology Development Strategy 2015–2020 National Biotechnology Development Strategy (Biotech Strategy II) (2007, 2014)
China	Bioenergy High-Tech	The Bioenergy Roadmap (2012)
		13th Five-Year Plan For economic and social development of the People's Republic of China (2016–2020)
		The National Medium- and Long-Term Program for Science and Technology Development (2006–2020)
		National Modern Agriculture Development Plan (2011–2015)
		13th Five Year Plan for Strategic Emerging Industries (2016)
		13th Five Year Plan on Bioindustry Development (2016)
		13th Five Year Plan of Renewable Energy Development (2016)
		13th Five-Year Plan for the Environmental Health Work of National Environmental Protection (2016)
		13th Five-Year Plan for Energy Saving and Emission Reduction
		12th Five Year Plan on Bioindustry Development" (2012)
		12th Five Year Plan (2011–2015) on Agricultural Science and Technology Development (2012)
		12thFive Year Plan for National Strategic Emerging Industries (2012)
		Policies to Promote Quick Development of Biological Industry. 2009
Brazil	Research & Innovation	13th FYP for Science, Technology and Innovation (2016)
	Research & Innovation	Estratégia Nacional de Ciência, Tecnologia e Inovação 2016–2019" (2016)
	Bioenergy	Plano Decenal de Expansão de Energia 2023 (2014)
	High-Tech	PAISS (2012)
Canada	Green Economy	Biotechnology Strategy (2007)
	Forestry	A Forest Bioeconomy Framework for Canada (2017)
	Agriculture	Growing Forward 2 agricultural strategy (2013–2018)
Spain	Holistic Bioeconomy Development	British Columbia Bio-Economy
	Regional Bioeconomy Development	Extremadura 2030 (2017)
Australia	Holistic Bioeconomy Development	The Spanish Bioeconomy Strategy—2030 Horizon (2016)
	High-Tech	Queensland Biofutures 10-Year-Roadmap and Action Plan (2016)
United kingdom	Blue Economy	National Marine Science Plan 2015–2025 (2015)
	Research & Innovation	National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (2013)
	Bioenergy	Opportunities for Primary Industries in the Bioenergy Sector: National Research, Development and Extension Strategy(2011) + Workplan (2014)
	Regional Bioeconomy Development	Strategic Roadmap for Australian Research Infrastructure (2011)
	High-Tech	Building a Bioeconomy in South Australia (2011–2015)
Italy	Holistic Bioeconomy Development	UK Synthetic Biology Strategy Plan Biodesign for the Bioeconomy (2016)
		Building a high value bioeconomy: opportunities from waste (2015)
		Biorefinery Roadmap Scotland (2015)
		Science and Innovation Strategy for Forestry (2014)
		Agri-tech Industrial Strategy (2013)
		High-value Manufacturing Strategy (2012)
		UK Bioenergy Strategy (2012)
Natural Environment White Paper (2011)		
UK Biomass Strategy (2007)		
Bioeconomy in Italy: A unique opportunity to reconnect economy, society and environment (2017)		

Source: Self-production based on Governance of the Bioeconomy: A Global Comparative Study of National Bioeconomy Strategies (2018) and of the report of the German Council on Bioeconomics (2018).

works on issues about the characterisation, and utilisation of agricultural wastes over the 65 year period. Agricultural wastes, as field of study, are mainly focused on Agricultural and Biological Sciences, 26% of the total articles published cover this area.

Environmental Sciences, as subject category has had special relevance over the last 13 years. Together with the study trend towards bioproducts and bioenergy production and participation of other environmental variables in the processes of use, transformation and utilisation of harvest wastes, this reflects an international trend related to understand agricultural economic growth.

In recent years, the increase in the number of publications related to a sustainable agricultural model is a good indicator of the changes taking place in public policies and the new regulatory framework. The growing interest in this subject, especially since 1998, is possibly a reply to government measures and actions, such as the call made by the General Assembly of the United Nations to world leaders through the report entitled "Our Common Future" of the World Commission on Environment and Development, published in 1987. This document highlights the urgency of proposing and implementing environmental strategies that would allow economic growth based on sustainable development. The conference of the "Earth Summit",

celebrated in 1992, allowed the consolidation of the approach on the need for a new model of sustainable development that considers the integration of economic, social and environmental factors, to guarantee the welfare and the improvement of the quality of life of the populations.

In addition, the fact that the totality of the scientific production analysed (3148 articles) was developed by public institutions, mainly government agencies, academic institutions and research centres, shows the important role that new policies have played in sustainable development. These new policies have had an impact on local development plans and programs because more and more funds are being invested in research, innovation and technological development. These are fundamental aspects in the process of transitioning to a circular economy model. Thus, the results obtained allow us to identify that those countries in which the highest scientific production has been generated have had higher rates of financial investment in R&D&I, especially in recent years.

The Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) of 2010 and the new Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development of 2015 are also indicators of the efforts made by governments to define strategies to transform their economies towards low-carbon production models. The main principle is the use of renewable natural resources and by-products, such as agricultural waste biomass, which is one of the main inputs to the bioeconomy. This is the main reason that over 60% of the articles analysed have been published in the last 10 years.

The previous considerations provide an answer to one of the questions of this study: “Are there any links between research on agricultural waste and the policies and/or guidelines issued under the sustainable development model?”. Undoubtedly, in recent years, bioeconomy policies and strategies, which have been defined and implemented by the countries that were the object of this research, have contributed to promote studies about the analysis of techniques and/or alternatives for the use and exploitation of agricultural residues. In reference to the second research question, “Have the techniques for the recovery of agricultural waste changed during the period analysed?”, this study discusses how the foundations of this new biological-based economic model have raised the need to improve and diversify the techniques and methods for the recovery of agricultural waste, in order to guarantee resource efficiency, sustainable production and the reduction of emissions and negative environmental impacts.

One of the questions presented by this research is whether the new global framework on sustainable development affects the local policies in all countries to the same degree. In addition, one of the countries with the highest scientific production of agricultural waste (Egypt) does not have a clear policy or strategy on bioeconomics. For this reason, the question is what other aspects motivate governments, research groups and in general the actors involved in the subject to develop this type of research. In addition, one of the future lines of research could be an analysis of the results of the research and their application or facility of implementation in the countries, to be able to judge whether public spending contributes to the objectives set in the local bioeconomy policies. The analysis of scientific production contained in other databases would also allow for a more complete and detailed analysis of this subject.

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